

Metadata description of 2D multichannel seismic reflection raw data

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Keywords: NFDI4Earth, DAM, metadata, Seismic Data, Marine Geophysics, SEG-D, SEG-Y

Changelog:

Version	Date
Version 1.0.0	31.01.2025

1 Introduction

The German marine seismic community aims to develop a standard for archiving seismic data, including both raw and processed field data. The main goal is to adhere to the **FAIR** principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable; Wilkinson et al., 2016) while ensuring compliance with the EU INSPIRE directive [3]. The motivation behind this standardization is two-fold: 1) to archive all new 2D multichannel seismic reflection raw data collected on German research vessels and 2) to provide interoperability with existing repositories and portals worldwide like MGDS [4], SDLS [7], SNAP [9], Geo-Seas [2] (Diviacco et al., 2016), and SeaDataNet [8] (Diviacco et al., 2012).

The NFDI₄Earth Pilot German Marine Seismic Data Access [5] (Berndt et al., 2023) was funded by the German Research Foundation (NFDI₄Earth, DFG project no. 460036893). It provides the basis for this standardization and was an initiative of the working group Marine Geophysics AGMAR of the FKPE (Forschungskollegium Physik des Erdkörpers). Within this working group, it was agreed to establish a common standard for 2D multichannel reflection seismic raw data taking into consideration different recording procedures.

The basis for the proposed metadata standard is the SEG-D seismic data standard for raw data (Society of Exploration Geophysics, 2015), with the flexibility to accommodate older versions, such as version 1.0, where necessary. The philosophy behind the SEG-D format is that the data are being written to a new file for every shot. This procedure ensures that only a minimal amount of data will be lost in case of disruptions. In analogy to this, we propose to generate a metadata file for each of the shots that have the same name convention as the SEG-D files. The combination of FFID (Field File Identification Number) and CRUISE ID are the unique keys required to identify the files.

The standard has been developed in collaboration with the German initiative DAM Underway Research Data [1] (Mehrtens et al., 2023; Berndt et al., 2024) and the repository PANGAEA [6] (Felden et al., 2023) to assure interoperability. For German research vessels, the ultimate goal is that all raw data and metadata are already copied to the Mass Data Management system (MDM) during a cruise and that the users (PIs) can fulfil their data management responsibility with minimal effort. The MDM is currently installed on the research vessels RV MARIA S. MERIAN, RV METEOR, RV SONNE and RV POLARSTERN.

We propose that the standard should become part of standard operating procedures (SOPs) in the different institutions. As the cumulative volume of seismic data per cruise can be very large (greater than 500 GB, status 2023) compared to other offshore data sets, the community should aim to obtain similar outputs, such as logs, metadata, and navigation files. SOPs tailored to each system can help streamline the process and reduce the workload associated with archiving datasets in PANGAEA.

Please note that the metadata for 2D multichannel reflection seismic raw data is still in the testing and development phase. Implementation has already begun, but adjustments will be made to adapt this standard to different systems. For example, the University of Bremen and the University of Hamburg will use SEG-Y as their file format, in line with the configuration of their recording systems.

This metadata description contains all the metadata definitions related to the first test cruise, SO294, conducted by Michael Riedel (GEOMAR) offshore Canada (Riedel & Cruise Participants, 2022; Riedel et al., 2024). Additionally, it includes a section that lists the selected metadata for the Marine Data Portal Viewer, ensuring that researchers can easily access all the essential information at a glance.

As an example, to illustrate the complete metadata description for our purposes, an ASCII file from a randomly chosen shot (Shot 2037) has been selected. This file serves as the basis for creating a parameter file for data publication on PANGAEA.

2037.txt		
General	Cruise ID	50294_CLOCKS
General	FFID	2037
General	Creator	Michael Riedel
General	Contributor	GEOMAR
General	Data	Seismic Reflection
General	Description	2D MCS
General	Vessel	RV Sonne II
General	Area	Cascadia Subduction Zone
General	Date	13.09.2022 - 27.10.2022
General	File Name	2037.sgd
General	File Format	segd rev 1.0
General	REEL FORMAT	8058 - 32 bit, IEEE demultiplexed
General	Data Product	Raw
Source	Source	GGun Array
Source	Total Volume (cu in)	2840
Source	Pressure (psi)	2030
Source	Aim Point (Delay) (ms)	55
Source	Source Depth (m)	8
Source	Number of Guns	6
Source	Distance to Antenna dx (m)	0
Source	Distance to Antenna (dy m)	68.1
Receiver	Receiver	Streamer
Receiver	Number of Sections	23
Receiver	Number of total channels	184
Receiver	Number of Auxillary Channels	2
Receiver	Total active Cable Length (m)	287.5
Receiver	Cable Depth (m)	2
Receiver	Group Spacing (m)	1.5625
Receiver	Distance Near Channel dx (m)	9.4
Receiver	Distance Near Channel dy (m)	83.1
Acquisition	Sampling Interval	1000
Acquisition	Samples Per Trace	12000
Acquisition	Recording Delay	0
NMEA		
File: 2037 \$GPRMC,144100,A,4750.6109,N,12802.5942,W,005.0,101.6,210922,016.5,E*64, 14:41:01.57		

2 General Metadata

General Metadata provides a description of a 2D multichannel seismic survey, including general survey and project information in accordance with PANGAEA standards. Additionally, it contains basic details about the dataset itself.

This and the following chapters already include wording changes from the original shell scripts, as adjusted during quality control by the data curator.

Cruise ID

attributeID	Cruise ID – Required
Description	Unique identifier of the cruise. Typically, German cruises have a cruise number consisting of the letters identifying the vessel (M for Meteor, MSM for Merian, SO for Sonne, and so on) and the sequential cruise number. This is followed by an underscore and the cruise acronym that was defined in the cruise proposal. The naming convention needs to be modified (e.g., SO299-2 instead of SO299/2) to comply with UNIX file system requirements as UNIX does not allow the use of the forward slash (/) in file or directory names. The forward slash needs to be replaced with a hyphen (-) to ensure compatibility and avoid errors in file handling or processing.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Free form text
Units or options	--
Example	SO294_CLOCKS

FFID

attributeID	FFID – Required
Description	Unique identifier of the field file identify number (FFID), also known as the <i>shot point</i> . This is the number used to identify the data file. Sometimes there are more shots than field file identity numbers, e.g., if the recording system was not working. Thus, the FFID only exists for shots that have been recorded. The FFID has to be unique within each survey.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	2037

Creator

attributeID	Creator – Required
Description	Name of the principal investigator of the scientific cruise. Creator is considered to be the originator of the seismic data and the person responsible for data curation. Typically, this is the chief scientist of the cruise unless the data have been collected by a secondary user.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Free form text
Units or options	--
Example	Michael Riedel

Contributor

attributeID	Contributor – Required
Description	Name of the institution that provides the data.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Free form text
Units or options	--
Example	GEOMAR

Data

attributeID	Data – Required
Description	Identifier for what kind of data the SEG-D file contains. It could be seismic reflection or seismic refraction (data).
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	Seismic Reflection

Description

attributeID	Description – Required
Description	Description is a further characterization of the data. Allowed values are: SCS (single-channel seismic data), 2D MCS (2D multichannel seismic data), or 3D MCS (3D multichannel seismic data).
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	2D MCS

Vessel

attributeID	Vessel – Required
Description	Name of the research vessel. Allowed values: RV Sonne, RV Maria S. Merian, RV Meteor.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Free form text
Units or options	--
Example	RV Sonne II

Area

attributeID	Area – Required
Description	Name of the sea region in which the data have been acquired. Depending on the cruise it can be an entire ocean or a smaller geographical area.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Free form text
Units or options	--
Example	Cascadia Subduction Zone

Date

attributeID	Date – Required
Description	Duration of the cruise but not the date of the shot.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Date Range
Units or options	--
Example	13.09.2022 - 27.10.2022

File Name

attributeID	File Name – Required
Description	Name of the data file that contains the seismic data for the shot FFID. The format is FFID followed by a period and the file extension. This is typically ".sgd" but can also be ".segd".
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Alphanumeric with Symbols
Units or options	--
Example	2037.sgd

File Format

attributeID	File Format – Required
Description	Format of the seismic file. We have agreed this to be SEG-D rev 1.0.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	segd rev 1.0

REEL Format

attributeID	REEL Format – Required
Description	Format of the SEG-D file (see description above) as SEG-D allows different formats regarding the position of the least and most significant byte, the option to multiplex the data, and the dynamic range of the data.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	8058 - 32 bit, IEEE demultiplexed

Data Product

attributeID	Data Product – Required
Description	Meant as a human-readable descriptor and should be of the value "Raw" for this standard.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	Raw

3 Source Metadata

Source Metadata provides a description of a 2D multichannel seismic survey containing source information in detail.

Source

attributeID	Source – Required
Description	Descriptor of the seismic source. It can have the values GGun Array, GI Gun Array, Sleeve Gun Array, Sleeve Gun, G Gun, GI Gun, Water gun, Sparker.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	GGun Array

Total Volume

attributeID	Total Volume – Required
Description	The sum of all air gun volumes for the entire area (or the primary volume when using GI Guns). The volume is expressed in cubic inches (cu in).
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	cu in
Example	2840

Pressure

attributeID	Pressure – Required
Description	Air pressure at which the guns are being fired. The unit is pounds per square inch, psi (one psi = 6894.76 Pascals), which is the industry standard for measuring air pressure in seismic surveys.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	psi
Example	2030

Aim Point (Delay)

attributeID	Aim Point (Delay) – Required
Description	Delay in milliseconds between the trigger time and when the air gun array is firing. It represents the sum of any intentional delays, e.g., specified to the gun controller as an aim point, and additional delays and physical delays by the guns themselves. The delay has to be determined from the seismic data for example by comparing the first arrival time to the sea floor arrival time and the sea floor multiple arrival time.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	ms
Example	55

Source Depth

attributeID	Source Depth – Required
Description	Defining the depth of the seismic source in the water in meters.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	8

Number of Guns

attributeID	Number of Guns – Required
Description	Number of airguns.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	6

Distance to Antenna dx

attributeID	Distance to Antenna dx – Required
Description	Across track distance from the GPS antenna to the nominal center of the air gun in meters. The value should be positive for starboard offsets and negative for port offsets.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	0

Distance to Antenna dy

attributeID	Distance to Antenna dy – Required
Description	Along track distance from the GPS antenna to the nominal center of the air gun array in meters. The value should be negative forward and positive astern.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	68.1

4 Receiver Metadata

Receiver Metadata provides a description of a 2D multichannel seismic survey containing receiver information in detail.

Some metadata terms were added during curation to resolve inconsistencies encountered while creating the ASCII files onboard during the first test trial cruise (SO294).

Receiver Array

attributeID	Receiver Array – Required
Description	Description of the receiver type. Normally this should be a streamer with several hydrophone groups in several sections.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	Streamer

Number of Sections

attributeID	Number of Sections – Required
Description	Number of streamer sections.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	23

Number of Total Channels

attributeID	Number of Total Channels – Required
Description	Number of active channels plus the number of any auxiliary channels after the active channels. The active channels (traces) contain the data collected by each hydrophone group. There is one active channel per hydrophone group.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	184

Number of Auxiliary Channels

attributeID	Number of Auxiliary Channels – Required
Description	Reflects the fact that some recording systems record additional channels, e.g., for air gun hydrophones. These channels should be at the end of the SEG-D file. If no additional channels are used, the value should be set to 0.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	2

Total Active Cable Length

attributeID	Total Active Cable Length – Required
Description	Sum of all active sections in meters. This does <i>not</i> include the length of the lead-in cable or stretch sections.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	287.5

Cable Depth

attributeID	Cable Depth – Required
Description	Describes the nominal depth of the streamer that has been tried to achieve for example by the use of birds. The true cable depth is normally variable depending on vessel speed, wave action, and currents.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	2

Streamer Attribute

attributeID	Streamer Attribute – Required
Description	The streamer attribute should reflect the streamer setup, including birds, LAUM preamplifiers, and other components. The input may need to be updated with every setup change.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	Compass birds

Group Spacing Constant

attributeID	Group Spacing Constant – Required
Description	Only applies to streamer without the extras: If the streamer does not include extras (e.g., LAUM preamplifiers or additional bird sections), the corresponding metadata field should be set to True . With the extras, please state False .
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Controlled vocabulary
Units or options	--
Example	False

Group Spacing Nominal¹

attributeID	Group Spacing Nominal – Required
Description	Spacing of the receiver groups, measured in meters. This value should equal the active cable length divided by the number of groups (i.e., the total number of channels minus auxiliary channels). If Group Spacing Constant is set to True , a specific value is required (e.g., 1.5625).
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Numeric or N/A
Units or options	m
Example	n/a

Distance Near Channel dx

attributeID	Distance Near Channel dx – Required
Description	Lateral offset from the GPS antenna to the first channel of the streamer in meters. It is negative for port offsets and positive for starboard offsets.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	9.4

Distance Near Channel dy

attributeID	Distance Near Channel dy – Required
Description	Offset along track from the GPS antenna to the first channel of the streamer in meters. It is negative for forward offsets and positive for astern offsets.
Required	True
Type	Float
Style	Numeric
Units or options	m
Example	83.1

¹ When **Group Spacing Constant** is set to **False**, the field should be set to 'n/a.' During dataset preparation for archiving, the correct values are added as a list. This functionality will be updated in a future version.

5 Acquisition Metadata

Acquisition Metadata provides a description of a 2D multichannel seismic survey containing acquisition information in detail.

Sampling Interval

attributeID	Sampling Interval – Required
Description	Specifies how often the seismic amplitudes are recorded in the seismic trace in microseconds.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	μs
Example	1000

Samples Per Trace

attributeID	Samples Per Trace – Required
Description	Number of samples per trace. Samples per trace times the sampling interval defines the recorded time.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	--
Example	12000

Recording Delay

attributeID	Recording Delay – Required
Description	Especially for high-resolution seismic data, the amount of time, the seismic waves spend below the seafloor, is small compared to the amount of time it spends in the water column to avoid recording of these data it is possible to start recording only closer to the seafloor. This is specified as recording delay in milliseconds.
Required	True
Type	Integer
Style	Numeric
Units or options	ms
Example	0

NMEA

attributeID	NMEA – Required
Description	String consisting of the keyword "File:" plus FFID plus the GPS NMEA string with the shot time in UTC.
Required	True
Type	String
Style	Pattern-based
Units or options	--
Example	NMEA File: 2037 \$GPRMC,144100,A,4750.6109,N,12802.5942,W,005.0,101.6,210922,016.5,E*64, 14:41:01.57

6 Marine Data Viewer Template Mapping

This chapter provides a list of metadata displayed for 2D multichannel seismic surveys. To ensure consistency and align with the terminology standards of PANGAEA and the Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) requirements (Konopatzky et al., 2023), some metadata terms used in the Marine Data Portal viewer (Frontend) have been adjusted.

Frontend (Display Name in Marine Data Portal Pop-up)	Backend (Technical Name Web Service)
Source (DOI)	source
PANGAEA Dataset ID	dataset_id
Download Link	download_link
Profile	profile
File Name	file_name
FFID	ffid
File Suffix	file_suffix
REEL Format	reel_format
Source	seismic_source
Total Volume	total_seismic_source_volume
Pressure	seismic_pressure
Source Depth	water_depth_of_gun
Number of Guns	number_of_guns
Receiver Array	receiver_array
Cable Depth	cable_depth
Streamer Attributes	streamer_attributes
Timestamp	date_time
Latitude	latitude
Longitude	longitude
Citation	citation
License	license
Platform	platform
Platform Type (NERC L06 SeaVoX Platform Categories)	platform_type
Call Sign	call_sign
IMO Number	imo_number
Campaign Name	expedition_name
Campaign Optional Name	expedition_alias
Cruise Report (DOI)	campaign_uri
Campaign Start	campaign_start
Campaign Start Location	campaign_start_location
Campaign End	campaign_end
Campaign End Location	campaign_end_location
Expedition Program	expedition_program
Project Label	project_label
Project Name	project_name
Project URI	project_uri
PANGAEA Processing Level	processing_level
PANGAEA Curation Level	curation_level
Added	created_at
Last Update	updated_at

PANGAEA 2D MULTICHANNEL SEISMIC REFLECTION RAW ... X

▼ SOURCE & DOWNLOAD

Source (DOI) <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANG...>

PANGAEA Dataset ID 961490

▼ FILE INFO

Profile P5014

File Name 30502.sgd

FFID 30502

REEL Format 8058 - 32 bit IEEE demultiple...

Source GI Gun

Total Volume 355

Pressure 2030

Source Depth 2

Number of Guns 1

Receiver Array Streamer

Cable Depth 2

Timestamp 2022-10-03T08:19:10Z

Latitude 49.583785

Longitude -128.30537

▼ REFERENCES

Citation Riedel, Michael; Bialas, Jörg; K...

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▼ CAMPAIGN & PROJECT INFO

Platform Sonne

Call Sign DBBE

IMO Number 9633927

Campaign Name [SO294](#)

Campaign Optional Name CLOCKS

Cruise Report (DOI) https://doi.org/10.48433/cr_so...

PANGAEA 2D MULTICHANNEL SEISMIC ... 2 X

Citation Riedel, Michael; Bialas, J...

Source (DOI) <https://doi.org/10.1594/P...>

Profile P5014

Platform Sonne

Campaign Name [SO294](#)

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Appendix 1 – Abbreviations

AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung [Alfred-Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar- and Marine Research]
BGR	Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR) in Hannover [Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources].
DAM	Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung [German Marine Research Alliance]
FAIR	
FKPE	Forschungskollegium Physik des Erdkörpers [Research Association for Earth Physics]
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe
MCS	MultiChannel Seismic
MDM	Massendatenmanagement [Mass Data Management]
MGDS	Marine Geoscience Data System
NFDI ₄ Earth	National Research Data Infrastructure for Earth System Sciences
PI	Principal Investigator
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SDLS	(Antarctic) Seismic Data Library System
SEG	Society of Exploration Geophysicists
SEG-D	SEG – Demultiplexed File format used for recording and storing seismic data in the field
SEG-Y	Standardized file format defined by the SEG for storing and exchanging seismic data
SNAP	Seismic data Network Access Point
SOP	Standing Operation Procedure

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[6] [PANGAEA] <https://pangaea.de/>

[7] [SDLS] <https://sdls.ogs.trieste.it/cache/index.jsp>

[8] [SeaDataNet] <https://www.seadatanet.org/>

[9] [SNAP] <https://snap.ogs.trieste.it/cache/index.jsp>

Appendix 3 – Changelog (extended version)

Version	Date	Comment
Version 1.0.0	31.01.2025	Release